

EcoCommons

Roadmapping our community needs - a user survey on data and environmental modelling

A strategy to engage our user communities to identify needs, barriers and opportunities in environmental modelling through an online open survey that targeted EcoCommons' 7000 registered users and new 'potential' users. This report documents survey findings and recommendations that will inform the development of EcoCommons.

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BACKGROUND

EcoCommons' vision is to give Australian practitioners and researchers access to trusted, world-leading ecological and environmental modelling tools. Through a three year (2020-2023), \$5 million investment from nine partner institutions, EcoCommons will transform ecological and environmental research by creating a trusted single national research infrastructure platform for digital modelling and analyses needs.

As work progresses toward the development of the platform, it is critical to identify and engage key stakeholders early and regularly in this process and ensure EcoCommons can fulfil its Mission and Vision. Stakeholder engagement and developing measures to track how EcoCommons improves the national research infrastructure will be an integral part of EcoCommons' development roll out. This stakeholder engagement activity reflects a 'roadmapping community needs exercise' by surveying existing and new potential users of the EcoCommons services.

This roadmapping exercise links to the following implementation plan deliverable:

D22 - Road mapping: open consultation meetings on the requirements in environmental modelling and report

The roadmapping exercise has these key objectives:

1. Gather requirements to identify user needs and validate the usefulness of proposed services.
2. Scope conditions under which key stakeholders would share sensitive data to inform EcoCommons' approach to Sensitive Data Havens.
3. Map the broader context of EcoCommons' community including barriers, trends and opportunities driving change.
4. Publish findings in an internal report.
5. Consider which findings can be turned into a public facing communications piece and/or a scientific publication.

The engagement approach - open online survey

Community needs and requirements were gathered by means of an online survey open to the public between January and March 2021. The survey targeted 7000+ registered users (with BCCVL and ecocloud), current stakeholders, and new potential users that features specific questions related to the use of sensitive data. The collection of data from ~400 survey respondents was analysed and the finding documented.

This report showcases findings from the 'EcoCommons: Data and Modelling in Science survey'.

The survey was conducted under Griffith University Ethics Approval (GU Ref No: 2020/889)

SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS

Through this process, close to 400 individuals from approximately 150 organisations contributed information about their data, environmental and ecological modelling needs and challenges. What users need from EcoCommons can be summarised into the following key themes:

WHAT DO THE RESPONSES TELL US?

- There is an appetite for EcoCommons amongst our existing and potential user communities.
- Confirmation that EcoCommons' work packages are focussed on the right things.
- User authentication, ethical data treatment and privacy of a Sensitive Data Haven are valued more than the availability of a particular analysis functionality.
- A refocus of ecoEd to upskill users in digital literacy and coding skills within the EcoCommons platform is recommended.
- Currently, our communications channels do not reach an industry audience. This requires a new targeted approach.

INSIGHTS FROM EXISTING USERS

There are clear trends for existing platform users. For example, existing users focused their responses on areas they would like to see some improvement in based on current services such as the [BCCVL](#), [ecocloud](#), [CSDM](#) and [ecoEd](#) (Table 1).

Existing **student** users generally requested more training materials to help guide them through the modelling process whilst experienced **researchers** would like to see more advanced model settings and a streamlined approach between access to fit-for-purpose data and analytics.

Government scientists would like to be

able to collaborate easily and have a way to standardise models, model outputs and data.

Table 1. Existing user needs and opportunities analysis based on survey responses

User type	Needs	Barriers	Opportunities
Students (undergraduate, masters, doctoral)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster, more user-friendly platform • More datasets • More detailed training materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coding • Limited understanding of models • Access to datasets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preferred ecoEd modules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Coding ○ Modelling and model selection ○ Platform use
Researchers (early, mid and senior)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Streamlined access to data and models • Advanced model settings • Model guidance • Collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to fit-for-purpose datasets • Access to shared code and data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data explorer with curated collections and access to CSIRO’s Knowledge Network • Provide means of sharing code, models and data • Updated scientific workflows and new workflows
Educators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Access to standardized datasets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited understanding • Coding • Access to shared code and data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preferred ecoEd modules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Coding ○ Modelling and model selection ○ Platform use • Data explorer with curated collections and access to CSIRO’s Knowledge Network
Government scientists and researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration • Access to datasets • Standardised models, model outputs and data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to fit-for-purpose datasets • Access to shared code and data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide means of sharing code, models and data • CSDM • Data explorer with curated collections • Updated scientific workflows and

scientists and researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to fit-for-purpose data • Limited collaboration 	resources through Analysis Playground <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curated collections in the Data explorer
Private sector scientists and researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and code sharing • Access to datasets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to datasets • Coding • Limited collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide means of sharing code, models and data

USER DEMOGRAPHICS

Types of respondents

- 394 respondents:
 - 26 % undergraduate students
 - 17% doctoral students
 - 9% early career researchers
 - 8% university academic staff
 - 8% government sector scientists/researchers

Other examples of respondents included eResearch staff, data scientists, Government analysts, consultants and engineers.

Figure 1. Number of survey respondents per user type

Location of respondents

The highest number of respondents were located in:

- New South Wales (28%)
- Queensland (15%)
- Western Australia (12%)

Approximately 32 respondents were from overseas. They are mostly based in China, the United Kingdom, United States and other countries including from Europe, Asia and South America.

Figure 2. Number of survey respondents per state and territory

Work place

The majority of respondents either work or study at:

- a university (66%)
- within the government sector (13%)
- a private organisation (8%)

Most common universities included Macquarie University, Griffith University, Deakin University, Charles Darwin University, University of Queensland, University of Adelaide, University of New South Wales, University of Western Australia, and University of Melbourne among many others.

Figure 3. Word cloud of universities where respondents were affiliated with

Figure 4. Number of survey respondents based on work and study place

Level of qualification

Respondents highest qualification varied from:

- Bachelor's degree (26%)
- Doctorate degree (21%)
- Masters degree (17%)
- High School Certificate (16%) - those are likely to be undergraduate students who have not yet completed their degree

Figure 5. Highest level of qualification of survey respondents

Area of science

Respondents' area of science varied:

- 60% ecology, conservation and biodiversity
- 34% environmental monitoring and management
- 25% climate change
- 10% social science
- 9% agriculture
- 8% geoscience
- 7% health
- 6% biosecurity
 - Few respondents were from public policy, atmospheric science or public health

Other fields that were included were data science, marine biology/science, physical sciences and statistics.

Figure 6. Area of science that respondents either work or study in

PLATFORM USE

Use of platforms

BCCVL

Of the 394 survey responses:

- 150 respondents had used the BCCVL, of which:
 - 43% were undergraduate students
 - 25% postgraduate students
 - 10% government sector employees
 - 9% early career researchers and high school students
 - 8% university academic staff
 - <5% were mid-career or senior researchers, school educators or private sector scientists/researchers
 - Of the 150 respondents that had used the BCCVL, 35% were undergraduate students who are studying ecology, conservation and biodiversity.

The BCCVL is mostly used for:

1. Research (22%)
2. Assignments (22%)
3. Reporting (4%)
4. Decision-making (3%)
5. Other
 - a. A number of 13 respondents reported that they use the BCCVL for teaching and training purposes.

Figure 7. Common uses for the BCCVL

ecocloud, CSDM, ecoEd

Of the 394 survey respondents:

- 8% had used the ecocloud or CSDM, of which:
 - The majority were undergraduate students or government sector employees

Of the 394 survey respondents:

- only 4 % had used ecoEd materials
 - The majority were undergraduate students and school or university staff.

Non-users

Interestingly, 36% of survey respondents had never used any of the services

Figure 8. Number of respondents who have used current EcoCommons services (BCCVL, ecocloud, CSDM, ecoEd) vs respondents who have never used these services

Platform satisfaction

Overall the majority of respondents were either satisfied or very satisfied with each of the current services. There was only a small number of respondents that were dissatisfied (Figure 9).

Figure 10. User feedback on current services including the BCCVL, CSDM, ecocloud and ecoEd

Citations

Many respondents indicated that they have cited the current services in:

- Assessment items
- Teaching material
- Scientific publications
- Organisational or government reporting and
- in conference materials

While many others have not cited the services at all.

Figure 11. Number of users that have cited the current services including the BCCVL, ecocloud, ecoEd or CSDM

MODELLING NEEDS

Experiments

The most preferred experiments that respondents would like to run were:

1. Species/multi-species Distribution Models
2. Climate change models
3. Biodiverse models
4. Species trait models
5. Migratory species models
6. Community models
7. Biosecurity risk mapping
8. Ensemble models

Other experiment types included plant disease, tensor flow machine learning, statistical analysis, temporal model evaluation, population dynamics and ecosystem models, population abundance modelling, population genetic models, hydrodynamic biophysical modelling, systematic conservation planning (Marxan, prioritizr) and energy infrastructure modelling.

Figure 12. The importance of each experiment type that users would like to run

Algorithms

The most preferred algorithms by respondents were:

1. Generalized linear models
2. Bioclim
3. Generalized additive models
4. Random forest
5. Classification tree
6. Artificial neural networks

Other algorithms that respondents listed included general dissimilarity models (GDM), hierarchical bayesian models, occupancy models, resource allocation models, dispersal models, tensor flow machine learning and Maxent.

*Note that Maxent was missed from the survey list of possible algorithms and as such was mentioned 9 times in the 'other' question. Knowledge from carrying out a scientific literature review has identified that Maxent is the most popular algorithm for species distribution modelling reported in scientific research.

Figure 13. The numbers of preferred algorithms which respondents use in their modelling experiments

Technical challenges

Respondents faced a number of technical challenges including difficulty in choosing which models to use, understanding model outputs, finding and processing datasets and a lack of computing power to run their analyses. These challenges varied per user type.

For **students** and **academic staff**, the most difficult technical challenges in ecological and environmental modelling are:

- understanding what the model outputs mean
- knowing which model to choose
- finding and processing datasets
- the need for advanced coding skills
- computing power and resources

For **researchers**, the most difficult challenges are:

- finding datasets
- knowing which model to choose
- understanding what the model outputs mean

For **government** sector scientists/researchers, the most difficult challenges are:

- processing datasets
- finding datasets
- understanding what model outputs mean

Open text responses provided some insights on the technical challenges of the users including:

- Coordination of effort and [model] outputs in a production line process
- Data available is too broadscale
- Difficult to get data in adequate format - [data wrangling] takes too long.
- Difficult to reuse models in a different context
- [Difficult to reuse models for] future climate scenarios
- Government competition and data silos
- IT infrastructure at work [is] not good enough, need online compute resources
- Lack of Fairness, Facts and Truths, Lack of Equality amongst PEOPLE, ...
- Lack of understanding the diversity of models
- Limited flexibility
- Managing very large datasets [is challenging]
- Many complex problems are NP hard
- [Data on] marine GIS layers are lacking
- My study system and species data often does not have the expected data structure (small invertebrates moving in small scales)
- [Lack of] secure data storage
- Sometime [the service] it is unavailable in some browser (chrome, edge, brave)

Figure 14. Technical changes faced by each user type

Technical needs

The most common suggestions to address technical challenges were to:

1. Provide documentation on model guidance to increase confidence in model selection, interpretation and reporting
2. Provide in-depth training materials on modelling
3. Provide better access to datasets including climate, environment and species
4. Provide methods for collaboration
5. Provide high power computing resources

Figure 15. Common needs for users to overcome their technical challenges

Advancement of ecological and environmental modelling

Common themes were prevalent when respondents were asked what they would like to see in the advancement of ecological and environmental modelling in the next 5-10 years.

Themes included:

- Access to more and better [more fit-for-purpose] data
- Better models including advanced settings, model validation and faster run time
- In general respondents want modelling to be user-friendly and available for first time users
- Increased collaboration including sharing of data and code to make the process more reproducible and transparent
- Streamlined access to both data and models
- In-depth training on what models to use and how to interpret the outputs
 - Less common responses included a community and ecosystem based approach
 - Increased compute power
 - Uptake of research in decision-making

Figure 16. Key themes that respondents hope to see in the future for ecological and environmental modelling

SENSITIVE DATA

Of the 394 respondents, 69 (17.5%) had worked with sensitive data such as threatened species or indigenous data, of which:

- 10% of respondents were BCCVL users
- 3% of respondents were ecocloud and CSDM users
- Only 2 respondents were ecoEd users

Figure 17. Number of respondents who have worked with sensitive data and are users of either the BCCVL, CSDM, ecocloud or ecoEd

User types

The majority of respondents who had worked with sensitive data were:

1. Government sector scientists or researchers
2. Bachelor degree students
3. Doctoral degree students
4. Mid-career researchers and
5. University academic staff

Figure 18. Respondents who have worked with sensitive data per user type

Information users would want before using an EcoCommons sensitive data haven

The most important information that users want to know before using a sensitive data haven include:

1. Data information such as use, source, ethics, location, metadata and statistics
2. Protocols and terms of use including data sharing, privacy and security compliance
3. User authentication

Figure 20. Listed benefits of using a sensitive data haven by each user type

TRAINING

The most popular preferred training methods were:

1. Training workshops
2. Webinars

Respondents typically prefer the following training format:

- One-two hours long or self-paced learning modules
- Some respondents preferred half-day training
- Few preferred full-day training or 5-10 minute training bites

Figure 21. Respondents preference for training format and duration

Generally respondents prefer communication to be via:

- E-newsletters
- Colleagues [word of mouth]
- With fewer respondents preferring social media such as facebook, twitter, linkedin or instagram

Attachment 1

Survey questions and raw data

n = 396 survey respondents

1. Which applies to you?
 - School student (n = 21)
 - School educator (n = 10)
 - Bachelor degree student (including Honours) (n = 106)
 - Master's degree student (n = 28)
 - Doctorate degree student (n = 68)
 - University Academic staff, Tutor, Lecturer, Professor (n = 32)
 - Early career researcher (n = 35)
 - Mid-career researcher (n = 23)
 - Senior researcher (n = 14)
 - Government sector scientist/researcher (n = 32)
 - Private sector scientist/researcher (n = 12)
 - Other [option to type an answer] (n = 15)

2. Where are you currently based?
 - Australian Capital Territory (n = 14)
 - New South Wales (n = 109)
 - Northern Territory (n = 12)
 - Queensland (n = 60)
 - South Australia (n = 24)
 - Tasmania (n = 3)
 - Victoria (n = 26)
 - Western Australia (n = 49)
 - Other [option to type an answer] (n = 68)

3. Where do you work and/or study?
 - University (n = 262)
 - Government (n = 51)
 - Private organization (n = 31)
 - NGO / non-profit / charity (n = 17)
 - School (n = 10)
 - Other (option to type an answer) (n = 5)

4. What is your highest level of qualification?
 - High School Certificate (n = 64)
 - Diploma, Advanced Diploma, Associate Degree (n = 13)
 - Bachelor Degree, Bachelor Honours Degree (n = 103)
 - Graduate Certificate, Graduate Diploma (n = 12)
 - Master's Degree (n = 68)
 - Doctorate Degree (n = 86)
 - Other [option to type an answer] (n = 50)

5. Which area do you work or study in? [multiple checkboxes possible]
 - Ecology, conservation, biodiversity (n = 235)

- Climate change (n = 100)
- Environmental monitoring and management (n = 153)
- Geosciences (n = 33)
- Atmospheric sciences (n = 13)
- Social sciences (n = 40)
- Health sciences (n = 28)
- Biosecurity (n = 24)
- Agriculture (n = 34)
- Public health (n = 11)
- Public policy (n = 16)
- Other [option to type an answer] (n = 43)

6. Have you ever used any of these services?

- BCCVL (n = 150)
- ecocloud (n = 33)
- ecoEd (n = 10)
- CSDM (n = 33)
- I have never used these services (n = 141)

7. What was your primary purpose of use of these platforms?

- Assignments (n = 85)
- Research (n = 86)
- Decision-making (n = 12)
- Reporting (n = 17)
- Other (option to type an answer)

8. How satisfied were you with your experience using the platform/s?

- Options: Very Satisfied (VS); Satisfied (S); Neutral (N); Dissatisfied (D); Very Dissatisfied (VD); Never used it (Never)
- BCCVL (VS = 29; S = 88; N = 27; D = 6; VD = 1; Never = 12)
- ecocloud (VS = 7; S = 18; N = 12; D = 3; VD = NA; Never = 102)
- CSDM portal (VS = 8; S = 20; N = 11; D = 2; VD = NA; Never = 103)
- EcoEd (VS = 8; S = 20; N = 11; D = 2; VD = NA; Never = 103)

9. What could be improved about your experience using the platform/s?

[option to type an answer]

10. Have you used or cited any of the platforms in the following

- Teaching material (n = 28)
- Conference materials (n = 13)
- Assessment item (n = 77)
- Scientific publication (n = 20)
- Government reporting (n = 14)
- Organizational reporting (n = 14)
- No, I haven't (n = 60)
- Other [option to type an answer]

11. What experiments are most important to you?

- Species/multi-species distribution models

- Species trait models
- Migratory species models
- Climate change models
- Biodiverse models
- Ensemble models
- Biosecurity risk mapping
- Community modelling
- Other (option to type an answer)

12. What algorithms / models are most important to you?

- Artificial Neural Network (n = 45)
- Classification Tree (n = 51)
- Generalized Linear Model (n = 129)
- Flexible Discriminant Analysis (n = 7)
- Generalized Additive Model (n = 68)
- Generalized Boosting Model (n = 19)
- Multiple Adaptive Regression Splines (n = 27)
- Random Forest (n = 53)
- Surface Range Envelope (n = 13)
- Boosted Regression Tree (n = 28)
- Bioclim (n = 74)
- Circles (n = 5)
- Convex Hull (n = 28)
- Geographic Distance (n = 38)
- Inverse-Distance Weighted Model (n = 32)
- Voronoi Hull Model (n = 5)
- Other [option to type an answer]

13. What are the main technical challenges you currently encounter in your work or study? [multiple options possible]

- Difficult to find datasets (n = 112)
- Difficult to process datasets (n = 98)
- Difficult to share and collaborate (n = 47)
- Difficult to repeat experiments (n = 29)
- Difficult to reproduce experiments (n = 30)
- It involves too much coding (n = 67)
- Hard to know which model to choose (n = 147)
- Difficult to understand what model outputs mean (n = 104)
- It requires too much computing power and resources (n = 72)
- Other [option to type an answer]

14. How would you like these technical challenges addressed?

[option to type an answer]

15. How would you like to share and collaborate on model development? What stops you from doing this now?

[option to type an answer]

16. In the next 5 - 10 years, what would you hope to see in the advancement of ecological and environmental modelling?

[option to type an answer]

Themes concluding from this question:

- Cannot answer this question
- More standardization of models
- Run multiple models and compare their outputs
- More training on what model to use
- Better uptake of research in decision-making
- More user-friendliness, especially for first time users
- Better models (run faster, account for uncertainty, contain AI algorithms, have more features)
- Offer users more compute power and share resources between users Empower easier use for a wide range of applications
- Unreasonable expectations
- A community/ecosystem-based approach
- More sharing of data and code for reproducibility
- More streamlined access to data and models
- Better data (at no cost, fine resolution, better standardization, long-term data, citizen science data)

17. What are your main needs from platform such as EcoCommons?

18. Have you ever worked with sensitive data such as threatened species or Indigenous data?

Options:

- Yes (n = 69)
- No (n = 135)

19. If a safe and well managed data haven was created, what would you want to know before using it? [option to type an answer]

20. What benefits would a safe data haven bring you? [option to type an answer]

21. What would you value most from EcoCommons in training and upskilling?

[option to type an answer]

22. What format do you prefer for your training and upskilling?

- Conferences (n = 39)
- Webinars (n = 121)
- Training workshops (n = 129)
- Networking events (n = 37)
- Hacky hours (n = 41)
- Other [option to type an answer] (n = 29)

23. What duration do you prefer for your training and upskilling?

- 5-10 minute bites (n = 48)

- One - two hours (n = 127)
- Half-day (n = 62)
- Full-day (n = 21)
- Go-at-your-own-pace series of modules (n = 97)
- Other [option to type an answer]

24. How do you find out about upcoming events, training and updates?

- Twitter (n = 45)
- Facebook (n = 54)
- Instagram (n = 11)
- LinkedIn (n = 33)
- E-newsletters (n = 122)
- Colleagues (n = 97)
- Other [option to type an answer]